

PREDICTING AND OPTIMIZING FDM PRINT PERFORMANCES AN AI APPROACH TO MECHANICAL PROPERTY OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Additive Manufacturing (AM), particularly Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM), enables the creation of intricate geometries with remarkable design freedom. Despite these advantages, the mechanical properties of FDM-fabricated parts are highly sensitive to variations in printing parameters and testing conditions. This work introduces an advanced machine learning framework aimed at accurately predicting the mechanical performance of polylactic acid (PLA) specimens, both in their pure form and when reinforced with natural fibers such as flax and wood flour. The methodology centers on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), specifically employing a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture that incorporates Gaussian and Gumbel-Gaussian activation functions. To address the challenge of high-dimensional process data, an encoder module based on a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) is integrated, enabling efficient data compression and feature extraction. The predictive capability of the model is further enhanced through a boosting neural network strategy and the application of a kernel-based truncated Taylor expansion, which together improve the model's ability to capture complex, nonlinear relationships between process parameters and mechanical outcomes. Experimental validation demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach. The model achieves a low Continuous Ranked Probability Score Normalized (CRPSN) of 0.072, indicating high predictive accuracy. Additionally, the framework delivers a substantial improvement over a mean baseline, with a Skill score increase of 67%. Multi-Objective optimization carried using Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-III) while inferring the trained neural network led to fast and accurate process' parameter optimization toward user defined desired mechanical properties. Experimental analysis performed by DSC confirmed the numerical relationships extracted by the two-step framework. Furthermore, results showed the proposed approach as a robust tool for guiding process optimization and material selection in additive manufacturing applications, paving the way for more reliable and tailored component performance within the constraints of AM technologies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) stands as a cornerstone of Additive Manufacturing (AM) due to its accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and capacity for fabricating complex geometries. Its adoption has rapidly expanded from prototyping to end-use parts in sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and biomedical engineering, where the demand for customized, lightweight, and high-performance components is ever-increasing.

The intricate interplay between FDM process parameters affects microstructure, interlayer adhesion, and, ultimately, the mechanical behavior of printed specimens. This complexity poses significant challenges for accurate prediction and optimization of mechanical properties, necessitating advanced modeling approaches. In recent years, Machine Learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for capturing the nonlinear and high-dimensional relationships inherent in AM processes. ML techniques have been successfully applied to predict both material and physical properties of FDM-fabricated parts. For example, Veeman et al. [1] developed a model to predict Rockwell hardness of ABS using process parameters and micrographs, while Castro et al. [2] utilized a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network to forecast compressive strength from time-series sensor data, achieving high predictive accuracy. Wei et al. [3] integrated Takagi–Sugeno fuzzy inference with multilayer neural networks to optimize FDM parameters for PLA, resulting in significant strength improvements. Charalampous et al.

[4] and Shi et al. [5] further demonstrated the utility of supervised learning and feedforward neural networks for optimizing mechanical behavior and predicting properties of FDM-printed polymers. Surface quality, another critical aspect, has been modeled using artificial neural networks (ANNs) by Chinchankar et al. [6] and Vahabli and Rahmati [7], the latter employing genetic algorithm (GA) optimization for parameter selection in medical applications.

Beyond property prediction, ML-driven approaches have been leveraged for geometric and process optimization in AM. Vaissier et al. [8] introduced a GA-based framework for optimizing lattice support structures, iteratively evolving parameters to minimize weight while maintaining mechanical integrity. The integration of ML and GA has also been explored for material discovery and multi-material design, as demonstrated by Borg et al. and Goh et al., respectively. Sondagar et al. [9] and Kosarac et al. [10] highlighted the effectiveness of ANNs in optimizing process parameters and machining conditions, even with limited datasets.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), in particular, have demonstrated significant potential in modeling nonlinear dependencies within both large and small datasets. Sondagar et al. utilized ANNs to predict optimal process parameters in additive manufacturing, focusing on improving mechanical properties and dimensional accuracy. The ANN was trained on experimental datasets with inputs including temperature, speed, and layer thickness and enabled nonlinear mapping between parameters and quality metrics. Kosarac et al. optimized machining parameter using ANN trained on small datasets.

Recent studies highlighted as promising innovation direction the integration of Genetic Algorithms (GAs) for multi-objective optimization of FDM process parameters. GAs, inspired by natural selection, are adept at navigating complex, multi-dimensional search spaces to identify optimal or near-optimal solutions. In AM, GAs have been applied to optimize build orientation, packing, scheduling, and process parameters, often in conjunction with ML models to enhance both prediction and optimization capabilities. For example, hybrid ML-GA frameworks have been developed for sustainability optimization, surface roughness minimization, and mechanical property enhancement in FDM [11], with the Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm [12] (NSGA-II/III) frequently employed for multi-objective tasks. These approaches have demonstrated superior performance in balancing competing objectives such as strength, surface quality, and production efficiency, and have been validated through experimental studies and case analyses.

Recent studies have also explored the combination of GAs with neural networks for precision prediction and inverse design in FDM. Yang and Zhang [13] established a GA-optimized Backpropagation (BP) neural network model to improve dimensional accuracy predictions, showing that GA optimization significantly enhances model performance by avoiding local minima and improving convergence. Similarly, integrated frameworks combining LSTM networks with GAs have enabled efficient inverse design of 3D printed parts to meet target mechanical properties, further underscoring the synergy between ML and evolutionary algorithms in AM optimization.

Traditional Artificial Neural Network (ANN) architectures frequently encounter difficulties when dealing with high-dimensional process data and the intrinsic variability associated with Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) printing [14], [15]. These challenges become particularly pronounced when numerous printing parameters are varied simultaneously, especially across wide ranges or near the mechanical limits of the 3D printer. To mitigate these issues, prior studies have typically limited their focus to a small subset of key parameters [16], [17] such as Extruder Temperature, Infill Type, and Infill Density, while holding other variables constant to improve model accuracy. However, this approach falls short of capturing the full complexity of the printing process, as it neglects intricate parameter interactions, thereby restricting the model's applicability in real-world scenarios that demand higher precision and process control.

To overcome these limitations, a novel machine learning framework has been developed, centered on a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [18] architecture augmented with a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) [19]. This design facilitates effective dimensionality reduction and feature extraction from complex input data. The framework is further enhanced by incorporating a boosting neural network strategy alongside a truncated Taylor series kernel applied to the model outputs, collectively boosting generalization performance and predictive accuracy for both physical and mechanical properties.

This study aims to comprehensively map the entire spectrum of FDM process parameters to the mechanical behavior of polylactic acid (PLA) and its natural fiber-reinforced composites (including flax

and wood flour), even under data-scarce conditions and while pushing printing and testing parameters close to the machine's operational limits. The result is a robust modeling solution capable of learning the nuanced dynamics of the process across its full domain, making it suitable for complex, real-world applications. By leveraging the statistical boosting-enhanced architecture, the framework accounts for the stochastic nature of FDM manufacturing, providing not only point predictions but also the associated statistical distributions. Treating the FDM process as stochastic rather than deterministic allows for more reliable engineering estimations, such as confidence intervals for lower and upper bounds, as well as analyses of distribution characteristics like kurtosis and skewness. Furthermore, the application of SHAP value analysis and GA parameter optimization on the virtual model environment enabled both a deeper understanding of the observed manufacturing processes and an automatic, tailor-made, fast and accurate control on the specimen mechanical properties.

Extensive experimental validation on previously unseen data, including extreme conditions near the printer's mechanical constraints and across different polymer suppliers, confirmed the model's high accuracy and strong generalization capability. This positions the framework as a valuable tool for optimizing printing parameters and improving the mechanical reliability of components produced via FDM.

2 METHODS

2.1 Materials

The polymer filaments utilized in this study were commercially sourced from multiple suppliers. Neat PLA filaments were obtained from BambuLab, R3D, Sunlu, and Nanovia, while PLA filaments containing flax fibers and wood flour were acquired from Nanovia. All filament spools were kept in vacuum-sealed containers with silica gel desiccant packs and underwent additional drying at 55 °C for a minimum of 48 hours before the printing process.

2.2 Manufacturing process

During the 3D printing process, a variety of parameters play a crucial role in determining the final characteristics of the printed specimens. These parameters can notably impact heat transfer and mass flow within the extruder chamber and on the surface of the specimen, as well as influence the vibration frequency of the printer's frame.

To thoroughly assess how these printing variables affect the mechanical performance of the materials, all major process parameters were systematically varied across the full range permitted by both the equipment and the materials themselves. The specific ranges for each parameter are detailed in Table 1; except for the categorical Infill Type, these ranges represent the minimum and maximum values selected for each parameter.

Specimens were manufactured by using a BambuLab X1E, a commercial desktop 3D printer. The tensile specimen adhered to the ISO-527-2 (type 1BA, L0 = 30 mm) standard, with a nominal thickness of 2 mm and a nominal width of 5 mm. To capture the intrinsic statistical variation in the properties exhibited by the printing process, five specimens were realized for each set of parameters. In the presented analysis, the parameters intervals were maintained continuous, aside from the categorical or strictly discrete ones, and the tuples of values were chosen randomly using an uniform random distribution, within the interval boundaries, for each batch of specimens.

For each material, a total of 20 batches were realized with such criteria for a total of 100 specimens for material. Each one of them was composed by 5 specimens manufactured with the same parameters, accounting for the inner stochastic nature of the manufacturing process and thus allowing a more robust modelling. Each of those specimens were treated as single data entries to both allow a stronger modelling of the associated statistical distribution and to capture the influence of X and Y location on the build plate on the resulting mechanical properties. With those criteria, a total of 600 specimens have been manufactured and a total of 120 different parameters combinations have been explored.

Despite the relatively limited number of independent parameter combinations, typically a challenge for artificial neural network (ANN) modeling, especially in high-dimensional feature spaces, the proposed framework demonstrated strong predictive accuracy for all measured outputs. This highlights its effectiveness even under conditions of limited and unstructured data.

Table 1. Printing parameters intervals

Parameter	Intervals
Layer Height	0.1 mm – 0.28 mm
Line Width	0.4 mm – 0.8 mm
Number of Shells	1 – 4
Base Layers	1 – 4
Infill Type	<i>Cubic, Rectilinear, Honeycomb, Gyroid</i>
Infill Density	5 % – 100 %
Speed of Base Layers	10 mm/s – 500 mm/s
Speed of Infill	10 mm/s – 500 mm/s
Acceleration	50 mm/s ² – 13000 mm/s ²
Jerk	1 mm/s ³ – 9 mm/s ³
Extruder Temperature	190 °C – 240 °C
Heated Bed Temperature	25 °C – 60 °C
Chamber Temperature	25 °C – 60 °C
Filament Dryer Temperature	25 °C – 55 °C
XY Position	0 mm – 257 mm

2.3 Specimen characterization

2.3.1 Mechanical properties

The uniaxial tensile tests of all manufactured specimens were carried out on a Zwick/Roell Z2.5 universal testing machine, equipped with digiClip extensometer (by Zwick/Roell) to accurately measure the strain (Fig. 1b). Tests were conducted in displacement control, varying the crosshead speed in an interval of 1 mm/min - 50 mm/min. The same strategy used in the manufacturing process was used here, so the test speed was chosen randomly in the interval boundaries for each batch of specimens. Such an approach allowed us to capture different strain-dependent mechanical behaviours, thus increasing the ANN's generalization capabilities.

2.3.2 Thermal properties

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis of the materials was performed under a nitrogen flow of 60 mL/min (DSC 214 Polyma by Netzsch). Samples (around 10 mg) were placed in a aluminium concave crucible with a pierced lid and analysed according to the following thermal program: heating from 0 °C to 220 °C (5 min hold interval), cooling to 0 °C (5 min hold) and second heating to 220 °C, all steps performed with a rate of 10 °C/min. The thermal information gathered from this analysis have been used to enrich the input data for the modelling, leveraging the correlation between melting temperature and mechanical properties [20], thus enabling more accurate predictions.

2.4 Learning task

This study focused on examining how printing and testing parameters translate into the mechanical and physical properties observed in the specimens. This challenge can be framed as a multi-input-multi-output (MIMO) regression problem, where both the printing and testing conditions serve as inputs, and the resulting material properties are the outputs of interest. In the realm of computer science and artificial intelligence, the quality of the dataset is just as critical as the neural network's ability to generalize. To enhance the informational value of each data point, the input set was enriched by incorporating not only the thermal properties of the printed polymer but also its mechanical properties measured under standardized printing and testing conditions, including fixed strain rates.

The thermal information about the polymer and how it influences the printing process was introduced by defining four different relative temperatures defined as:

- $\Delta T_{\text{Text-melt}}$:= Extruder temperature - Melting temperature
- $\Delta T_{\text{bed-cryst}}$:= Heated bed temperature - Crystallization temperature
- $\Delta T_{\text{bed-glass}}$:= Heated bed temperature - Glass transition temperature

- ΔT_{bed-ch} := Heated bed temperature - Chamber temperature

Including the polymer's thermal properties in the model allowed it to distinguish between different polymers without relying on additional one-hot encoding schemes. This approach reduced the input dimensionality while establishing a meaningful correlation between the polymers' thermal and mechanical characteristics. Moreover, the temperature-dependent value shifts helped normalize the 3D printer's operating temperatures across different polymers, effectively creating a nearly uniform reference framework. This normalization eased the computational complexity of the modelling task.

Mechanical information was incorporated by producing six specimens per polymer using a fixed set of printing parameters consistent across all materials. These parameters were carefully selected to yield reliable and representative samples. For each polymer, half of the specimens were printed with a 0° raster angle and the other half with a 90° raster angle, allowing separate evaluation of the filament's intrinsic strength and the inter-layer bonding strength of parallel deposited filaments. Additionally, each polymer and raster angle combination were tested at three different strain rates, 5 mm/min, 20 mm/min, and 40 mm/min, to capture how mechanical behaviour varies with strain rate.

As a result of these enhancements, the input feature space expanded threefold, increasing from 25 to 75 features. However, the enriched data significantly offset the challenges of higher dimensionality, leading to a consistent improvement in the model's overall predictive accuracy.

2.5 Framework structure

The model architecture employed in this study is a multi-headed multilayer perceptron (MLP) featuring a Variational MLP Encoder (VE) as a shared backbone. In this design, the common backbone functions as an effective compressor that encodes and transforms the input features into a meaningful latent representation, while each individual head is dedicated to predicting a specific output feature.

Additive manufacturing (AM), particularly fused deposition modeling (FDM), operates in a partially observed environment where not all variables are known or controllable during production. To address this uncertainty, both the VE backbone and the MLP heads map their outputs onto Gaussian-shaped distributions, following approaches used in prior research dealing with uncertainty-driven scenarios. By producing statistical predictions rather than deterministic outputs, the model can more effectively navigate the loss landscape, reducing the risk of becoming trapped in local minimum.

This capability is achieved by duplicating each head and employing a Negative Gaussian Log Likelihood (NLL) loss function during training, which encourages the outputs to conform to Gaussian distributions. Consequently, the neural network can predict mechanical properties more accurately by providing both the expected mean and variance of each parameter, thereby capturing the uncertainty inherent in certain regions of the printing parameter space. For clarity, this type of neural network will be referred to as iBNN in the following sections.

To further explore the enhanced modelling capabilities offered by a more accurate statistical representation of the output, a similar NN (iBNNG) that maps the output features into a Gaussian-Gumbel [21] space has been realized.

The aforementioned statistical distribution can be defined as:

$$\bullet \quad Y_{pdf}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\bullet \quad \mu_{pdf}(x) = \frac{1}{\beta} e^{-\left[\left(\frac{x-\mu^*}{\beta}\right) + e^{-\frac{x-\mu^*}{\beta}}\right]} \quad (2)$$

Using this definition only three parameters – μ^* , σ , β – are needed to actually represent the distribution, and they can be modelled by three different neural networks. As with the previous approach, each neural network within the triplet is a replica of the original head, which effectively reduces the hyperparameter search space during optimization. These networks were trained using a Gaussian-Gumbel Negative Log Likelihood (GGNLL) loss function combined with the Gumbel-Max reparameterization trick, enabling gradient backpropagation throughout training. The use of different statistical representations in this study allowed the model to capture both the inherent stochasticity of

the process, by mapping outputs into a Gaussian distribution, and the occurrence of catastrophic defects within specimens, by mapping into a Gaussian-Gumbel distribution, thereby providing a more precise characterization of the process dynamics.

To prevent the hyperparameter space from becoming excessively large, the MLP architecture employed here features a sequential and consistent reduction in the width of hidden layers. This layer size reduction is governed by a user-defined decay parameter, which simplifies the architectural design to just four key parameters: the number of layers, the decay rate, the initial hidden layer size, and the type of activation function. The calculation of input and output layer sizes is straightforward and summarized as follows:

- Input size of i^{th} layer := $\text{round}\left(\max\left(\frac{\text{initial hidden size}}{\text{decay}^{i-1}}, 1\right)\right)$
- Output size of i^{th} layer := $\text{round}\left(\max\left(\frac{\text{initial hidden size}}{\text{decay}^i}, 1\right)\right)$

In the proposed framework to further improve the predictions, the increase in accuracy offered by the boosting architectures has been leveraged; thus, similarly to the famous XGboost [22], the proposed models have been built and trained subsequentially to refine the prediction of the previous models, until no further meaningful increase of accuracy was reached.

2.6 SHAP Analysis

Following the training of the iBNN and iBNNG frameworks, a statistical analysis was conducted to assess the impact of input parameters on the models' outputs using Shapley Values. Typically, Shapley values are applied in scenarios where individual contributors have unequal but cooperative roles in achieving a collective outcome or payoff. Within the application of machine learning and AI interpretability, this mathematical tool provides quantitative estimates of each input feature's influence on the model's predictions. In the context of this study, assuming the models are accurate, these values serve as proxies to reveal the true effect of process parameters on the resulting mechanical properties.

After calculating both SHAP values and SHAP interaction values for the iBNN and iBNNG models, the insights gained were used to develop a novel kernel-based AI approach that accounts for the lack of interaction between input parameters. This kernel was designed as a truncated Taylor series expansion, where the model's output approximates the k -th order derivatives and truncation error, and can be represented as follows:

$$Y(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=0}^K \frac{f_i^{(j)}}{j!} (x_i^j) \quad (3)$$

where:

- $f_i^{(j)}$ is the j -th derivative of a generic function, relative to the i -th input variable. In this context $f_i^{(j)}$ is approximated by the NN.
- x_i is the i -th input variable used in the i -th generic function, truncated at the K -order. Using this kernel, it was possible to force lower levels of interaction between input features, lowering the complexity of the optimization process.

The realized pseudo-physics informed NN (iPBNN) has been trained with the same methodology of iBNN and iBNNG, as shown in the next sections, truncation's degree was set as hyperparameter.

2.7 Dataset preprocess and training pipeline

The data preprocessing in this study involved a three-step procedure: one-hot encoding (OHE), scaling, and partitioning. Following scaling, the dataset was split into training-test and validation sets with a ratio of 95:5. Because selecting optimal test points for an accurate performance metric was challenging, a 10-fold cross-validation [23] approach was employed to more reliably assess the models' predictive capabilities.

Model architecture optimization was performed using a Bayesian algorithm aimed at minimizing the test loss averaged over the cross-validation folds. The training process consisted of two main stages. First, a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) was trained on the input data. Next, a multi-headed MLP was constructed using the best-performing encoder from the VAE (the Variational Encoder, VE) as the

shared backbone. During the initial stage, a sweep evaluated 10,000 VAE models, selecting the one with the lowest average cross-validation loss. In the second stage, each MLP head underwent 10 boosting rounds, with 500 models assessed per round. After each boosting round, the top-performing model was chosen to serve as the booster for the subsequent round. This procedure was repeated for all 10 output heads, resulting in a total of 60,000 models being trained and evaluated to complete the entire training process.

2.8 Genetic Optimization

Genetic based algorithms were used on the converged AI framework to optimize process parameters on user defined mechanical and process constraints. Process parameters have been clustered into different genes using as discrimination criteria the effect exerted on the process; thus, allowing a more stable phenotypic expression and a smoother optimization. Each gene, structural, cinematic and thermic, was characterized by their own mutations, crossover and inversion coefficients to allow independent mutation dynamics and efficient hyperparameter search. Furthermore, mutation, inversion and inversion coefficients were also subjected to mutation and crossover rates to allow a smoother transition from the exploration to the exploitation stage. Finally, to allow a multi-objective optimization avoiding hierarchical objective function definition, NSGA-III [24] algorithm was used, with a population of 2048 individuals and with 100 generations per optimization.

AI fine-tuning was also performed to stabilize the NN prediction, avoiding numerical instabilities that could have occurred in interpolation or extrapolation regions. A Physic-Informed NN (PINN) criteria was then used, forcing a hierarchical relationship between the output parameters, for example Force UTS always greater than Force Yield. Since the defined soft-constrained PINN was characterized by multiple loss functions, a self-adaptive loss balanced algorithm was used to allow a faster and smoother convergence [25].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented in the following sections. To avoid the bias associated with training and test datasets, which tend to favor overfitting, only predictions on the validation set are reported. Since conventional accuracy metrics like Mean Absolute Error (MAE) or Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) are not directly suitable for evaluating probabilistic forecasts, the Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS) was employed as a generalized version of MAE for probabilistic predictions. By generating an empirical distribution (F) through N samples drawn from the probability density function, the CRPS is defined as follows:

$$CRPS(F, x) = \sum_{k=0}^x F(y_k)^2 + \sum_{k=x+1}^n (F(y_k) - 1)^2 \quad (4)$$

where n is the last element of the right tail of the PDF. To allow comparisons and a common metric through the output features, a pseudo Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) has been also introduced, based on CRPS values, called CRPS Normalized (CRPSN). Formally it has been defined as:

$$CRPSN(F, x) = \frac{CRPS(F, x)}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{x \in D} x_i} \quad (5)$$

where the denominator is the mean value of the real observed output feature. Additionally, to facilitate a more straightforward comparison of accuracy across different models, an extra metric called Skill was introduced. This metric quantifies the improvement in accuracy relative to a naïve prediction, which is simply the mean of the observed values. Formally, the Skill metric is defined as:

$$Skill(F, x) = \frac{CRPS(x_{mean, x}) - CRPS(F, x)}{CRPS(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{x \in D} x_i, x)} * 100 \quad (6)$$

Lastly, to provide a more practical assessment of the models' reliability, an additional metric called the Confidence Region Score (CR score) was introduced. This metric is calculated using the 2.5th and 97.25th percentiles (Q(0.025) and Q(0.9725)), which together capture approximately 95% of the distribution's statistical significance. The CR score represents the average frequency with which the

actual observations fall within this $\pm 2\sigma$ interval, meaning a higher score indicates a stronger alignment between the observed data and the predicted statistical distribution. Although this metric is unconventional, it enabled effective comparisons between the different statistical outputs of the model. Meanwhile, the CRPS metric provided a quantitative measure of error analogous to the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), facilitating more precise evaluations of the models' accuracy.

3.1 Framework predictions and Ablation Study

Table 2 presents CRPSN values on prediction for mechanical properties and physical properties relative to iBNN framework and its variants.

The iBNN predictions show increased variance under certain printing conditions, particularly at high Toughness values, highlighted by a high value in CRPSN for iBNN, iBNNG and iPBNN. This elevated variance is attributed to the significant statistical variability caused by unpredictable internal defects such as inclusions, under-extrusions from inconsistent filament diameter, and thermal degradation. These defects serve as nucleation points for voids and cracks, substantially reducing the specimen's maximum energy absorption and strain capacity.

Table 2. CRPSN values for every output feature, calculated on the validation partition for the proposed models, the baseline models, and the ablation study models.

Model	Rigidity	Force UTS	Strain UTS	Force Yield	Strain Yield	Strain Break	Toughness	b	h	P Tot	Mean
SVM	0.069	0.126	0.108	0.108	0.109	0.253	0.320	0.008	0.016	0.041	0.116
XGB	0.100	0.160	0.117	0.154	0.107	0.372	0.379	0.014	0.016	0.054	0.147
iBNNH	0.054	0.106	0.098	0.098	0.085	0.150	0.212	0.006	0.014	0.031	0.085
iBNN	0.045	0.073	0.065	0.062	0.068	0.172	0.182	0.005	0.011	0.040	0.072
iBNNG	0.049	0.114	0.073	0.103	0.083	0.175	0.189	0.005	0.014	0.058	0.086
iPBNN	0.035	0.062	0.041	0.062	0.084	0.176	0.292	0.004	0.012	0.034	0.080
BMLP	0.062	0.066	0.079	0.044	0.071	0.178	0.183	0.006	0.014	0.036	0.074
BNNH	0.067	0.091	0.067	0.078	0.102	0.147	0.183	0.006	0.016	0.048	0.080

Notably, the rise in confidence region values occurs consistently across all output features for the same input conditions, indicating that each model head has effectively and independently captured the process dynamics. This ability to learn variances linked to printing and testing parameters enables the model not only to predict mechanical properties in advance but also to identify and avoid parameter regions prone to unpredictable defects. Despite these high-variance regions, the models reliably capture the specimens' mechanical and physical behavior, as evidenced by consistently low CRPSN scores across all output features.

An ablation study was conducted on the proposed framework by systematically removing key components: first the Gaussian head, then the Variational Encoder, and finally the engineered input features. For clarity, models trained without engineered features are referred to as BNN and BNNG. Models without the Gaussian head are labeled BNNH and iBNNH, following the previously established naming convention. When both the head and backbone were removed, the resulting architecture became a standard Boosted MLP, referred to as BMLP. For baseline comparison, XGBoost (XGB) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models were also included and optimized using the same Bayesian Optimization process as the main study.

Across nearly all output features, these simplified and comparative models showed higher CRPSN values than the full models. Traditional approaches like XGB and SVM also exhibited higher CRPSN values compared to both the complete and ablated neural network models. These results highlight that the proposed framework offers superior prediction accuracy in complex, highly stochastic scenarios such as FDM, outperforming conventional modeling techniques.

3.2 SHAP Analysis

AI modelling is frequently regarded as a black-box technique, effective at delivering accurate predictions but often lacking transparent and straightforward explanations of the underlying mathematical processes driving those predictions. To address this limitation, a statistical SHAP analysis was performed to uncover the physical relationships between the input variables and the model's output predictions.

The results reveal key insights into the process dynamics from a materials science perspective. For rigidity, the relative density of the specimen was the most influential factor, with lower density reducing stiffness. Additionally, a larger temperature difference between the heated bed and printer chamber negatively affected rigidity, likely due to uneven internal stresses. A similar negative correlation was observed between rigidity and the difference between extruder temperature and polymer melting point, suggesting thermal degradation of PLA, flax fibers, and wood powder. High jerk values also reduced rigidity, indicating that strong vibrations during deposition harm mechanical properties.

For toughness, the X position on the build plate had the strongest negative impact, implying that vibrations and thermal gradients near chamber walls cause defects that reduce energy absorption. Unlike rigidity, toughness was more sensitive to abrupt changes in acceleration rather than the speed of those changes. Structural parameters like shell and base layer count positively influenced toughness, highlighting the role of filament orientation. A strong negative correlation with layer height suggested the formation of meso-crystalline phases during printing, which enhance energy absorption during testing.

This hypothesis was supported by DSC analysis (Fig. 3), showing significant enthalpy release around 90–98 °C in printed specimens before and after testing, attributed to residual stress release and fusion of process-induced meso-crystals [26]. The increase in crystallinity from 6.08% to 11.35% during tensile testing confirmed these meso-crystals contribute to improved toughness.

Table 3. DSC analysis on high plastic PLA specimen in the deformed region, the undeformed region, and the reference second heating as baseline.

Specimen	T _{cold-cryst} (°C)	T _{melt} (°C)	ΔH _{cold-cryst} (J/g)	ΔH _{melt} (J/g)	χ (%)
As Printed	67.6	160.06	-26.25	31.91	6.08
Tested	70.01	159.06	-23.04	33.36	11.35
Reference	107.3	159.9	-27.65	35.53	8.47

3.3 Genetic Optimization

Genetic optimization was carried out on the converged and fine-tuned iBNN AI framework. To prove its effectiveness a run was performed with the objective of maximizing the Force Yield, while minimizing the theoretical density of the manufactured specimen. The results of the optimization process are shown in Figure 1, where the algorithm successfully identified the Pareto optimality frontier associated with the proposed task. Furthermore, analysing the proposed optimality frontier, it was found a significant high frequency in solutions of PLA-Flax reinforced respect to PLA-Wood reinforced, suggesting a lower fiber-matrix interface in the latter composite composition. SEM analysis on the fracture surface of PLA-Wood reinforce specimen was conducted and it was confirmed indeed the absence of an interface between PLA polymer and the wood particles reinforcement; thus, confirming the purely data-driven relationship discovered by the combined application of both NSGA-III and iBNN frameworks.

Figure 1. NSGA-III optimization using iBNN as virtual environment, maximizing Force Yield and minimizing the theoretical density of the specimen.

4 SUMMARY

This study aimed to develop an AI framework that efficiently maps printing parameters and testing conditions to the mechanical and physical properties of 3D-printed specimens, covering a wide range of process variations. The proposed model, a Boosting multi-headed Variational Encoder MLP combined with a kernel-based truncated Taylor expansion, successfully predicts outputs in both Gaussian and Gaussian-Gumbel spaces. Validated on unseen data, the models achieved low CRPS values (0.080, 0.072, and 0.086 for iPBNN, iBNN, and iBNNG respectively), outperforming traditional methods like XGB and SVM by effectively capturing variance in highly uncertain FDM processes.

SHAP analysis revealed meaningful correlations between process parameters and mechanical properties, which were experimentally confirmed, demonstrating the model's ability to learn complex relationships in additive manufacturing. Leveraging the minimal interaction between inputs identified by SHAP, a Pseudo-Informed Neural Network was created using a kernel-based truncated Taylor expansion, further enhancing performance where standard PINN approaches are not feasible.

Overall, this methodology offers a robust solution for FDM and other AM techniques, maintaining accuracy despite high-dimensional, sparse data, common in real-world scenarios with limited data availability. The coherent insights from SHAP and NSGA-III also suggest its potential as a tool not only for prediction but for understanding process dynamics.

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